

Accumulation of carbonate rocks on Earth through time

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Abstract

A geological unidirectional process which runs throughout the Earth's history is quantitatively described: accumulation of carbonate rocks. Over the Phanerozoic, carbonate rocks accumulate in a nearly linear way, resulting in a quantity defined as one Phanerozoic accumulation unit. On the other end of this one-directional process, hydrothermal processes in mid-ocean ridges deliver calcium from oceanic crust into seawater. First estimated values of annual calcium fluxes (inputs) match very good with the average accumulations (output).

Like radioactive decay and entropy increases in isolated systems, the accumulation of carbonate rocks is a unidirectional process, which presents an example that materials in geological processes are not recycled. The accumulation process is a new concept which is to be taken into consideration when observing and investigating other phenomena and processes on the Planet. This new concept can give satisfactory explanations to the "excess calcium paradox" problem, where calcium masses in sedimentation are proportionally much more than those of other major elements.

Keywords: unidirectional processes, material recycling, accumulation, carbonate rocks

Introduction and data sources

Carbonate rocks exist on Earth for a very long time. The oldest carbonate rocks documented are 3.5 to 3.8 billion years (Ga) old (Lowe, 1980; Walter et al., 1980; Cantine et al., 2020). During the Archean, their formation may be inorganic precipitations or biogenic activities, or combination of both. Since the Cambrian and with the appearance of skeleton during the Ordovician, biogenic is dominating in the formation and production of carbonates (Cantine et al., 2020).

After formation, carbonate rocks undergo a series of losing processes such as weathering and erosion, dissolution and translocation, subduction and volcanism, separately or combined with tectonic and other processes. Despite all these processes over a very long time, some of them survive and exist on Earth up to now. These are the so-called extant carbonate rocks which we observe all over the planet.

Extant carbonate rocks are very well documented (Cantine et al., 2020; Hay, 1985; Lowe, 1980; Morse & Mackenzie, 1990; Peter et al., 2018, Ronov, 1982; Ronov et al., 1980; Ronov et al., 1991; Walter et al., 1980; Wilkinson & Walker, 1989 and references therein). In a series of publications (Ronov, 1982; Ronov et al., 1980; Ronov et al., 1991), Ronov and co-workers documented the Earth's sedimentary shell through the Earth's history. With a combination of a "volumetric method" (Ronov, 1947), geological maps, and direct analyses of borehole samples, they compiled volumes and chemical compositions of sedimentation on global continents.

Many authors (Cantine et al., 2020; Hay, 1985; Morse & Mackenzie, 1990; Peter et al., 2018; Wilkinson & Walker, 1989) treat Ronov's data as one of the most comprehensive global compilations with detailed quantitative description of carbonate and other rocks, and they used them as a database for further investigation and discussion. In this article, data from Ronov's publication serves as the main data source.

Accumulation of carbonate rocks throughout the Phanerozoic

Table 1 lists extant carbonate rocks throughout the Phanerozoic Eon. Column 2 are volumes of extant calcium carbonate sedimentation of the corresponding period or epoch in column 1. Columns 1 and 2 are excerpts from Table 13 of Ronov et al. (1980). Column 3 changes column 2's volume into weight, using a density of 2.53g/cm^3 for carbonate rocks (Ronov et al., 1980). Column 4 adds the weight of column 3 together, setting beginning of the Phanerozoic Eon as the origin point (weight = 0). Column 5 is the age in million years (Ma), where Age = 0 is the Present.

Table 1: Extant calcium carbonate rocks throughout the Phanerozoic

<i>Column 1</i>	<i>Column 2</i>	<i>Column 3</i>	<i>Column 4</i>	<i>Column 5</i>	<i>Column 6</i>
Period / Epoch	Volume [10 ⁶ km ³]	Weight [10 ²¹ g]	Weight sum [10 ²¹ g]	Age BP [Ma]	Rate [10 ¹² g/year]
Pliocene (N ₂)	0.18	0.454	363.006	2	65
Miocene (N ₁)	1.87	4.712	362.552	9	295
Oligocene (Pg ₃)	0.62	1.562	357.840	25	130
Eocene (Pg ₂)	4.59	11.567	356.278	37	551
Palaeocene (Pg ₁)	1.27	3.200	344.711	58	400
Late Cretaceous (K ₂)	10.73	27.040	341.510	66	795
Early Cretaceous (K ₁)	8.51	21.445	314.471	100	670
Late Jurassic (J ₃)	6.43	16.204	293.026	132	772
Middle Jurassic (J ₂)	4.44	11.189	276.822	153	746
Early Jurassic (J ₁)	4.32	10.886	265.633	168	640
Late Triassic (T ₃)	4.69	11.819	254.747	185	473
Middle Triassic (T ₂)	2.44	6.149	242.928	210	615
Early Triassic (T ₁)	1.60	4.032	236.779	220	269
Late Permian (P ₂)	1.82	4.586	232.747	235	229
Early Permian (P ₁)	11.12	28.022	228.161	255	1121
Late and Middle Carboniferous (C ₂₊₃)	8.91	22.453	200.138	280	561
Early Carboniferous (C ₁)	13.98	35.230	177.685	320	1409
Late Devonian (D ₃)	7.67	19.328	142.456	345	1289
Middle Devonian (D ₂)	7.73	19.480	123.127	360	1217
Early Devonian (D ₁)	3.69	9.299	103.648	376	387
Silurian (S)	5.07	12.776	94.349	400	365
Ordovician (O)	9.10	22.932	81.572	435	417
Late Cambrian (ε ₃)	6.62	16.682	58.640	490	667
Middle Cambrian (ε ₂)	7.75	19.530	41.958	515	651
Early Cambrian (ε ₁)	8.90	22.428	22.428	545	897
Phanerozoic (Ph)	144.05	363.006	363.006	570	637

Figure 1 (columns 4 and 5 in Table 1) shows the accumulation of carbonate rocks throughout the Phanerozoic. A continuous, almost linear increase of extant carbonate rocks can be observed. We introduce now the concept of sedimentation accumulation rate, ρ , of carbonate rocks, which is defined as the amount of extant carbonate rocks formed in one year during a specified time. Average accumulation rates of various periods and epochs over the Phanerozoic can be calculated by dividing the weight of carbonate rocks (column 3 of Table 1) by the duration of the corresponding period or epoch (Ronov et al., 1980). Results are presented in column 6 of Table 1 and in Figure 2.

Fig. 1 Accumulation of carbonate rocks over the Phanerozoic. The line is to guide the eye.

The carbonate accumulation rates are highly irregular (Fig. 2), exhibiting no clear trends to increase or decrease over the Phanerozoic. The accumulation rate averaged over the Phanerozoic, $\rho(\text{Ph})$, is the total weight of carbonate rocks (363×10^{21} g), divided by the Phanerozoic duration (570Ma, both data from Ronov et al., 1980), resulting in 637×10^{12} g/year, as the horizontal line in Fig. 2.

$$\rho(\text{Ph}) \text{ CaCO}_3 = 637 \times 10^{12} \text{ g CaCO}_3/\text{year} = 6.37 \times 10^{12} \text{ mol CaCO}_3/\text{year}$$

That is, on average, every year about 637×10^{12} g carbonate rocks are added to reservoirs or sinks and exist as extant sedimentation on Earth. The highest rates over the Phanerozoic are $1300 \sim 1400 \times 10^{12}$ g/year during late Devonian and early Carboniferous, and the lowest 65×10^{12} g/year during the Pliocene Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Accumulation rate of carbonate rocks over the Phanerozoic. The horizontal line is the average.

Accumulation of carbonate sedimentation has two characteristics. First, it is a one-directional process, extant carbonate rocks increase with time (Fig. 1). Second, the accumulation process has its fundamental nature of spontaneity. It is a process which happens all the time in nature. No other preconditions are needed for System Earth to make this process running. Other examples of such one-directional spontaneous natural processes are radioactive decay and increase of entropy in isolated systems.

Due to its character, many, if not all, phenomena and processes on Earth are to be observed and investigated from a new point of view, that is, taking into consideration of carbonate accumulation as a kind of process occurring all the time as “baseline” and “background”. Some examples are discussed in the next sections.

Ronov data are, in the author's view, the best currently available for discussing accumulation of carbonate rocks. There are newer data published, such as Hay (1985) who compiled carbonate sedimentation on ocean bottoms from present back to about 200 Ma ago, starting point of the Pangaea's breaking. Furthermore, no sedimentation on the Antarctic is considered in Ronov data. All carbonate rocks, with or without magnesium, are for the first approximation treated as calcium carbonate in this article. Antarctic data, Hay's data, and further results with more modern investigation and more detailed time divisions in the sedimentology will surely improve results and conclusions about carbonate accumulation.

Accumulation of carbonate rocks throughout Earth's history

Now we have a look into Precambrian carbonate rocks, starting from the very beginning of the Earth's formation. The Earth was a fireball of molten rocks at the beginning of its formation. Under these conditions, no carbonates in solid form could exist (thermal decomposition temperatures of carbonates are between 700° to 900°C). During the first 600Ma after the Earth's formation (the Hadean Eon), we hypothesize that the quantity of extant carbonate is zero. That is, carbonate rock which formed during Haden, if any, does not survive and exist up to now. This hypothesis is strongly supported by the fact that the oldest carbonate rocks documented are 3.5 to 3.8Ga old (Lowe, 1980; Walter et al., 1980; Cantine et al., 2020). In this way, carbonate accumulation rate over the Hadean is zero (Table 2).

Masses of carbonate rocks from Rhiphaean to Present (1.6 to 0 Ga) are documented in Table 7 of Ronov et al. (1980), which, together with the corresponding durations, are presented in Table 2. Masses of carbonate rocks before the Rhiphaean (1.6 to 4 Ga) can be calculated.

Total amount of calcium in sedimentation, expressed in CaO, is 0.239×10^{24} g (Ronov & Yaroshevsky, 1969; see also Table 4), or 4.27×10^{21} mole. Adding up of all carbonates from Rhiphaean to Present in Table 2 results in 407×10^{21} g, or 4.07×10^{21} mole. The difference between these two values,

$$4.27 \times 10^{21} \text{ mol} - 4.07 \times 10^{21} \text{ mol} = 0.2 \times 10^{21} \text{ mol} = 20 \times 10^{21} \text{ g CaCO}_3,$$

is then the amount of carbonate rocks before Rhiphaean (4 to 1.6Ga, Archean and Paleoproterozoic).

According to Milliman (1993), annual calcium carbonate production is 5.3×10^{15} g, of which 3.2×10^{15} g are accumulated in bottom sediments in the first year. To get a holistic

picture, this value, 3.2×10^{15} g, is treated as the accumulation of Year One and added in Table 2.

Table 2: Carbonate accumulation rate, ρ , throughout the Earth's history

Eon/era	Age [Ma]	Duration [Ma]	Extant carbonates [10^{21} g]	Rate ρ [10^{12} g/year]
Hadean	4000-4600	600	0	0
Archean + Paleoproterozoic	1600-4000	2400	20	8.3
Middle + Later Riphean	1100-1600	500	17.6	35
Upper Riphean	680-1100	420	15.2	36
Vendian	570-680	110	11.7	106
Phanerozoic	0-570	570	363	637
Present	0.000001	0.000001	0.0000032	3200

Now we have a complete picture of carbonate accumulation rate throughout the Earth's history (Fig. 3). The y-axis (in logarithmic) shows average accumulation rate and the x-axis the middles of each duration. For example, the x-value of the Phanerozoic is set in the middle of that eon at: $570/2=285$ Ma. This averaging makes a lot of details lost. Nevertheless, Fig. 3 gives a first overview of carbonate accumulation rate through time on Earth.

The rarity of carbonate sediments during the Archean has been noticed by many authors (e.g. Cameron & Baumann, 1972). From Archean to Paleoproterozoic (4 to 1.6 Ga), average accumulation rates are 8.3×10^{12} g/year, which are almost two orders of magnitude lower than those during the Phanerozoic (Fig. 3). This 8.3×10^{12} g carbonate rocks have a volume of 0.003 km³ which corresponds roughly to volumes of a hillock or a small hill.

During the Riphean (1600 to 680 Ma), a period of almost one billion years, accumulation rate was $35 \sim 36 \times 10^{12}$ g/year (Fig. 3), or 0.014 km³ /year, volumes roughly of a hill.

Starting from Vendian, especially during the Cambrian, production and with that accumulation of carbonate rocks increased explosively by more than one order of magnitude (Fig. 3). Average annual carbonate accumulation over the Phanerozoic is 637×10^{12} g, or 0.25 km³, volumes of a mountain.

Fig. 3 Carbonate accumulation rate through the Earth's history. The line is a guide to the eye. Pay attention that the y-axis is logarithmic.

In summary, from the Archean to late Proterozoic, a very long period of 3.3 billion years, carbonate rocks with volumes of a hillock or a hill are accumulated every year. During the Phanerozoic, the annual accumulation increases to volumes of a mountain. After billion years' accumulation, carbonate rocks are all over the global, in many places being one of the most prevalent elements on Earth's geomorphology and landscapes (Ford & Williams, 2007): the Great Barrier Reef, South China Karst, the Dolomites, to name just a few.

Sources for carbonate formation and accumulation

The carbonate rocks consist of four main elements: calcium, magnesium (mainly dolomite), carbon and oxygen. What are the sources of these elements which supply for generation and accumulation of the rocks for several billion years (Figs. 1 and 3)?

Here we define and distinguish two kinds of sources (or processes in a general sense): exogenic and endogenic. Exogenic sources are those that are recycled, and endogenic non-recycled. Exogenic, or surface sources, are those that move and recycle within the system

many times, that is, multi-directional. Endogenic, or deep sources, are those that come from outside of the system in a one-way direction, and thus one-directional. These two definitions are leaned on but not the same as those of Wolery and Sleep (1976).

Carbonate accumulation is an endogenic process, that is, after formation and all losing processes, survived carbonate rocks store permanently in reservoirs or sinks, forming extant carbonates rocks which stay outside of the system. Theoretically, carbonate rocks can be weathered, eroded or in other ways changed anytime and anywhere. If we observe then statistically, nevertheless, the accumulated rocks can be treated as being outside of the system and do not take part in any active processes.

Fig. 2 shows us that, on average, every year around 637×10^{12} g carbonate rocks leave the system as accumulation. A logical question is that from the other end of the process materials must be delivered into the system to keep the process “alive”, running for billions of years.

As a thought experiment we assume that the only sources for carbonate generation were materials in the atmosphere and the oceans and no recycling would happen, that is, all carbonates would accumulate after their formation. We calculate how long it would take to exhaust the elements in these sources when carbonate accumulates with a Phanerozoic average rate of 637×10^{12} g/year, or 6.37×10^{12} mole/year.

Table 3: Calcium and carbon in the atmosphere and oceans as sources

Element	Total mass in seawater³⁴	Total mass in the atmosphere³⁴	Years to be exhausted
Calcium	1.43×10^{19} mole	0	2.2 Ma
Carbon	6.3×10^{18} mole	9.8×10^{16} mole	1 Ma

Results in Table 3 tell us that after 1 Ma and 2.2 Ma, carbon and calcium, respectively, would be exhausted in the atmosphere and the oceans. Both are geologically very short times. It is, therefore, essential that long-lasting sources must be available to keep the accumulation processes running.

Hydrothermal processes have been first documented in the 1970s. The processes are interactions of oceanic crust volcanic basalts with seawater at elevated temperatures and pressures, resulting in, besides thermal effects, changes in seawater chemistry.

After discovery of the hydrothermal activities at mid-ocean ridges, simulations of the reactions have been carried out in laboratories under various conditions and parameters (Bischoff & Dickson, 1975; Hajash, 1975; Humphris & Thompson, 1978; Mottl & Holland, 1978). Two main results related to carbonate accumulation are: magnesium in seawater is almost completely depleted (transferred into the basalts); and calcium is delivered from the basalt into seawater. The main results in laboratories are in accordance with field observations (Tómasson & Kristmannsdóttir, 1972).

Despite careful design and experimentation, it is very difficult for laboratory investigation to simulate all the complexity of hydrothermal processes in real field (Wolery & Sleep, 1976). Nevertheless, basic trends and results have been achieved. Several authors (Wolery & Sleep, 1976; Edmond et al., 1979; Corliss et al., 1979; Elderfield & Schulz, 1996) have published first estimations of annual calcium flux, i.e., masses of calcium delivered from the basalts into seawater in one year, to be between 0.2 and 4.3×10^{12} mole. Data from Corliss et al. (1979) are 2.4 to 4.2×10^{12} mole. We use the middle value 3.3×10^{12} mole Ca/year for further discussion.

Now we have two data. One is calcium supply into the system via hydrothermal processes, 3.3×10^{12} mole Ca/year; and the other is calcium removal (accumulation), 6.37×10^{12} mole CaCO_3 /year. With these two data at both ends of the endogenic processes, a very nice picture of carbonate accumulation is established.

It is easily noticed that the input (3.3×10^{12} mole) is roughly only half of the output (6.37×10^{12} mole). Despite the difference, the data fill into the picture in a very satisfactory way. First, accumulation rate $\rho(\text{Ph})$ is an average over the whole Phanerozoic, during which it changes quite a lot (Fig. 2); while Ca flux is a few data decades ago. The accumulation rate of Pliocene, the nearest epoch to the present, is 0.6×10^{12} mole/year (Table 1), being the lowest of the whole Phanerozoic. The Pliocene value is only 20% of the hydrothermal Ca flux. The second point is that accurate data is very difficult to obtain due to complexities in hydrothermal activities (Wolery & Sleep, 1976), and much more difficult for data in the past. For a first estimation, comparable data within the same order of magnitude can be treated as very successful achievement. Future investigations and more data can certainly improve and refine the results.

The “excess calcium paradox”

By analyzing data of Ronov and Yaroshevsky (1969), Pytkowicz (1979, 1980), citing Loewengart (1975), noticed an abnormal distribution of calcium between sedimentation and the Earth’s crust. Ronov and Yaroshevsky (1969) published masses of major elements (expressed in their oxides) in the sedimentation distributed in three regions: continental, sub-continental and oceanic. The addition of the three regions results in the mass of that oxide in total sedimentation, expressed by S. Masses of element oxides in the whole crust are expressed by C. Data of S, C and ratios of S/C are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Masses of major element oxides in Earth’s crust and sedimentation (in 10²⁴g)

Element oxide	In Earth’s crust [C]	In sedimentation of different regions			Sediments total [S]	Ratio S/C
		Continental	Sub-continental	Oceanic		
SiO ₂	16.463	0.645	0.240	0.077	0.962	5.8%
Al ₂ O ₃	4.412	0.168	0.062	0.021	0.251	5.7%
FeO + Fe ₂ O ₃	1.928	0.074	0.027	0.011	0.112	5.8%
MgO	1.104	0.040	0.015	0.006	0.061	5.5%
K ₂ O	0.663	0.026	0.010	0.004	0.04	6.0%
CaO	2.002	0.151	0.056	0.032	0.239	12%

Major elements include Si, Al, Fe, Mg, K and Ca. S/C ratios of the first five elements are between 5.5% and 6% (Table 4). The S/C ratio of calcium oxide is, however, 12%, i.e., more than twice as high as others. This excess calcium in sediments is the so-called “calcium paradox” which Ronov and co-workers (Ronov, 1982; Ronov et al., 1980; Ronov & Yaroshevsky, 1969; Yaroshevsky 2006) considered to be the most enigmatic issue of geochemistry of the Earth’s outer shell and awaits still its resolution (Yaroshevsky 2006).

The root cause of this problem can be found with the concept of carbonate accumulation. Calcium enrichment in sedimentation is the result of three steps of carbonate accumulation. First, calcium, with its root in Earth’s mantle, comes into seawater via hydrothermal processes. Second, calcium in seawater is transferred, mostly via biogenic

processes, into calcium carbonate which, as the last step, sediments and accumulates as oceanic and later continental sedimentation. This from-mantle-to-sediment process results in, with time, enrichment of calcium in the sedimentation (Table 4).

The excess calcium as compared to other elements as shown in Table 4 is a “snapshot”, a value of the current Earth. Back in Earth’s history, this value was lower, starting from zero to 12%, in the same way as described in Figs 1 and 3, i.e., carbonate accumulation. Based on data in table 1, it can be calculated that during the Late Devonian (350 Ma ago) the calcium S/C value was 5.9%, the average S/C ratio of other major elements of the current Earth (Table 4).

Availability of elements for carbonate accumulation

The accumulation of carbonate rocks has been going on for billions of years (Fig. 3). How is the availability of materials for accumulation in the future? We first introduce a concept of Phanerozoic accumulation unit, U_{Ph} , which is defined as the quantity of a sedimentation accumulated during the Phanerozoic. Based on data in Table 1, one Phanerozoic accumulation unit of calcium carbonate rocks (sometimes simplified as one Phanerozoic unit), $U_{Ph(CaCO_3)}$, is 3.63×10^{21} mole.

Table 5 gives quantities of the four carbonate compositional elements: O, Mg, Ca, and C, in Earth’s primitive mantle (Lee et al., 2019; where mass of the primitive mantle is 4×10^{27} g) and compared with the Phanerozoic unit to get ratios of the corresponding elements. Ratio of oxygen is 30,303, meaning that the amount of oxygen in the primitive Mantle is more than 30 thousand times as needed for carbonate accumulation for the whole Phanerozoic. Up to now, just one unit has been used up. Availability of oxygen can thus be regarded as endless. Ratios of magnesium and calcium are, respectively, 10,000 and 716 (Table 5), and the availability of both elements can also be treated as endless.

The availability of carbon has very special features. Exact quantities of carbon in Earth’s reservoirs are highly uncertain (Lee et al., 2019). We take data published by Lee et al. (2019) and Falkowski (2000) as basis for our discussion. Part of their data is presented in Table 5. Concentration of carbon in primitive mantle is < 350 ppm which corresponds to a quantity of $< 2.3 \times 10^{23}$ mole. For convenience, we take the upper limit, 2.3×10^{23} mole, which is 63 Phanerozoic units and orders of magnitude lower than other carbonate elements (Table 5). Nevertheless, the availability of carbon for accumulation of another 62 Phanerozoic

periods (roughly 35 billion years) doesn't seem to be an issue, at least from a theoretical point of view.

Table 5: Masses of elements in Earth's mantle

Element	Reservoir	Concentration	Mass [mole]	Mass ratios to the Phanerozoic unit
Oxygen	Primitive mantle	44.33%	1.1×10^{26}	30,303
Magnesium	Primitive mantle	22.17%	3.6×10^{25}	10,000
Calcium	Primitive mantle	2.61%	2.6×10^{24}	716
Carbon	Primitive mantle	< 350ppm	$< 2.3 \times 10^{23}$	< 63
	Upper mantle	< 350ppm	$< 0.6 \times 10^{23}$	< 17
	Lower mantle	< 350ppm	$< 1.67 \times 10^{23}$	< 46
	Depleted mantle	30ppm	5.3×10^{21}	1.5

The upper and lower mantles in the primitive mantle have the same carbon concentration and their carbon ratios to the Phanerozoic unit are 17 and 46, respectively (table 5). The carbon concentration in the upper mantle has changed greatly since then. In the depleted mantle, carbon concentration decreases from < 350ppm down to 30ppm, which means that the carbon quantity in that reservoir has reduced from 17 to about 1.5 Phanerozoic units (Table 5).

Contrary to the theoretical consideration, the 1.5 Phanerozoic units of carbon reserve in the depleted mantle present a fundamental issue of carbon availability for future carbonate accumulation. First, volume fractions of the Earth's crust and upper mantles are 1.4%, and 26.5%, respectively (Lee et al., 2019). Carbon quantity in the crust is, depending on data sources (Ronov & Yaroshevsky, 1969; Falkowski, 2000), 1.2 or 1.4 Phanerozoic units. We take the middle value of 1.3. Combining the data, we get a ratio of carbon concentration in the crust and the upper mantle to be: 1 to 0.061. Upon an assumption of homogeneous distribution, carbon concentration in the crust is much higher than in the upper mantle. With this great concentration gradients, it is thermodynamically very unfavorable to transfer carbon from the upper mantle to the crust. Second, data from hydrothermal processes (Elderfield & Schultz, 1996) show that, instead of being a source, they are sinks for carbon. That is, via

hydrothermal processes carbon is transferred from seawater into the oceanic crust. Therefore, for the upper mantle to be a source of carbon, special mechanisms are yet to be discovered.

The carbon reserve in the lower mantle is much higher (Table 5). To become a potential source, carbon must be transported through the upper mantle to the location of carbonate production, i.e., in seawater. Like other deep carbon related subjects (Hazen et al., 2013), a lot of investigation is necessary to obtain a more detailed picture.

Carbons in the crust are roughly 80% stored in sedimentary carbonate rocks and 20% in kerogens, and in other pools together are < 0.01% and negligible (Lee et al., 2019; Flakowski et al., 2000). When carbonates are produced from decomposition products of older carbonate rocks, these newly formed carbonates do not statistically contribute to the accumulation because they are recycled. All extant carbonate rocks are therefore exogenic sources and they don't lead to new accumulation. Only substances from endogenic sources contribute to new accumulation.

The quantity of carbon in Earth's kerogens is 0.34 Phanerozoic unit (calculated from Flakowski et al., 2000) and they can be possible endogenic sources for carbonate accumulation. Like carbon in the lower mantle, the most important issue is again how it works to transfer and transport carbon into the production locations.

In summary, carbon availability for carbonate accumulation has the following features: carbons in the atmosphere and oceans are not sustainable sources. Carbons in extant carbonate rocks don't give rise to new accumulation. Carbons in the upper mantle as a source have several critical issues. Carbons in the kerogens and in the lower mantle could be possible endogenic sources but transportation related processes are yet to be investigated in detail.

Carbonate accumulation is an ongoing process. Extremely huge amounts of carbonate rocks have been accumulated, and the process is ongoing. Currently we do not have satisfactory answers to questions about carbon long-term availability. But we do know that it works in some way. New investigations, discovery of new mechanisms and new endogenic sources can add mosaics to finish the picture.

Stoichiometry

Carbonate rocks have a formula of CaCO_3 with an atomic ratio of $\text{Ca}:\text{C}:\text{O}=1:1:3$ (magnesium-containing carbonates can be discussed in a similar way). When calcium carbonates accumulate, they leave the system with this defined chemical stoichiometry. At the

other end of the accumulation process, substances with the same elements, the same quantities and the same stoichiometry come into the system. Input and output are in this way balanced.

It is highly unlikely and over the geological time impossible that the elements could come from a single source with the defined stoichiometry to supply carbonate production and accumulation for billions of years. There are several possibilities to keep the balance: elements from different endogenic sources, changes in ocean concentrations and other exogenic sources, endogenic addition or removal of one or several elements via processes other than carbonate accumulation. Many investigations and data are necessary to give satisfactory answers to this issue of stoichiometry balance. Here we just take seawater concentrations as an example.

Concentrations in seawater, their changes with time, and whether they are in a steady or non-steady state have been discussed by many authors (Ronov et al., 1982; Milliman, 1993). Discussions can be deepened by taking into consideration of the new concept of carbonate accumulation. More details and results are to be prepared in a separate paper.

Questions and discussions

As discussed above, the carbonate accumulation process consists of three steps: transportation, production and accumulation. First, all elements needed should be available on location of production (mostly the oceans); the second step is formation of carbonates, mainly biogenic; and the final step is accumulation of carbonate rocks in reservoirs and sinks after all losing processes. Within each step, there are many sub-steps and sub-processes.

Of the three steps of carbonate accumulation process, we now have the first solid data of the third step, i.e., carbonate accumulation quantities and rates through Earth's history (Figs 1, 2 & 3). Despite the enormous amount of literature on carbonate topics, documentations of the first two steps, especially data in the past, are very limited. We are therefore still at a very early stage to describe the carbonate accumulation process in a completely quantitative way. Some preliminary thoughts, questions and discussions are presented in the following.

Production and accumulation of carbonate rocks have continued on Earth for almost four billion years. A sharp rise in accumulation rate is during the Cambrian (Fig. 3). This increase correlates with the radiation of complex life and later appearance of skeleton (Cantine et al., 2020). Has this sharp increase something to do with changes in the supplies?

Were there possibly pull- or push-effects between supply and production? That is, were it due to the production increase and depletion of elements in seawater, extra sources were activated (pull-effects); or were it due to increase of element concentrations in seawater, precondition existed for increases in carbonate production and with that appearance of skeleton (push-effects)?

For calcium, the main exogenic source in seawater is river discharge (Morse & Mackenzie, 1990), and the main endogenic sources are hydrothermal processes (Wolery & Sleep, 1976; Edmond et al., 1979; Corliss et al., 1979; Elderfield & Schulz, 1996). How have these exogenic and endogenic sources influenced changes of accumulation rate shown in Figs 2 and 3? The concept of carbonate accumulation opens new fields with many questions

- Why can carbonate rocks accumulate over the Phanerozoic in an almost linear way (Fig. 1)?
- Why do accumulation rates scatter a lot over the Phanerozoic (figure 2)? Has this scattering something to do with other geological processes such as orogens and areas of epeiric seas?
- How have the sources for carbonate elements changed over the Earth's history? What would happen if there were large changes in the supplies?
- Are there correlations between big events on Earth history and possible supply changes and related production and accumulation rates?
- Are there other main endogenic sources besides hydrothermal processes?
- What are the main mechanisms of carbonate-forming elements and materials transported to location of production?
- Are there other one-directional geological processes?
- Almost all carbonate rocks are biogenic. Contrary to many geological processes where materials are recycled, carbonate accumulation is one-directional. Are there correlations between this one-way character and the biogenic?
- A possible comparison between biogenic and non-biogenic is a comparison between carbonate accumulation and accumulation of other sedimentation such as those from orogen processes. What does such comparison look like?

To the question “are materials in geological processes recycled?”, a spontaneous answer would be “yes, of course.”. An inquiry in Internet such as Google gives the same results. Now we’ve shown a counterexample: carbonate rocks are not completely recycled, but getting more and more throughout the Earth’s history, i.e., accumulation of carbonate rocks is a one-directional geological process.

The carbonate accumulation began with zero in the absolute sense, i.e., no solid carbonates existed at the beginning. With the accumulation, continental surfaces are covered more and more by carbonate rocks, which changes the conditions of exogenic sources. More continental covering results in more calcium delivery into the oceans. How do seawater concentrations and with that the carbonate production change accordingly? How does a picture of continent coverage by carbonate rocks over the Earth’s history look like? Would there be a point of no return in the future? Would there be a “Big Coverage” of the continent surface by carbonate rocks, analog to the “Big Freeze” (the heat-death of the universe)?

Final words

As time passes, radioactive substance decays and entropy in an isolated system increases, spontaneously. Now we have a further process: accumulation of carbonate rocks. Why do they accumulate? It is not difficult to answer this question from a geological point of view: because annual carbonate production is greater than all the losses added together. It is, however, much more difficult to answer this question from a philosophical point of view.

Are there some forces or rules behind the carbonate accumulation process? Does the accumulation have something to do with other one-way processes like radioactive decay and entropy increase, and, in a much deeper sense, with the everlasting onward moving of time itself (as Confucius, standing by the river, said: “...flowing away ceaselessly day and night”)?

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